

Conference Abstract

Flux map on tall towers: a study over heterogeneous landscapes

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Abstract

Monitoring fluxes of greenhouse gases is crucial to attribute sources and sinks. With advancements in satellite technology offering resolutions smaller than a tower's footprint, we can now have spatially-explicit estimations at the meter scale, a comparable resolution to in-situ observations. This study explores the potential of assimilating tall tower eddy covariance fluxes to calibrate a surface model of CO₂ exchange over a heterogeneous landscape. We present a bayesian inversion strategy which compares an estimated flux supposedly measured by the tower, calculated based on a priori flux map and a footprint model, and the observed flux. Two sites (Saclay and P2OA) are evaluated both consisting of a mix of agricultural, forest and urban patches. The heterogeneous landscape provides an ideal setting to assess the method's ability to distinguish and quantify greenhouse gas flux contributions from different land types.

Keywords

eddy covariance; tall tower; bayesian inversion; sentinel2;

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.